

The impact of accreditation on improving the quality of healthcare services: A literature review

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Abstract

Hospital accreditation plays a vital role in improving the quality and safety of healthcare services. This study aims to explore the impact of accreditation on enhancing hospital service quality by analyzing various related studies. Literature searches were conducted using Google Scholar, Portal Garuda, Elsevier, Springer, and PubMed databases with a search range from 2018 to 2024. The retrieved articles were filtered based on titles, abstracts, and keywords, resulting in 28 relevant articles. Of these, 15 articles (2015–2023) were selected for further analysis, while 13 literature reviews were excluded. The findings indicate that accreditation, whether by the Joint Commission International (JCI) or the National Accreditation Board for Hospitals and Healthcare Providers (NABH), significantly impacts hospital service quality. Accreditation positively influences resource utilization, patient satisfaction, professional standards, patient safety, and hospital operational performance. Key factors supporting successful accreditation implementation include leadership commitment, clear strategic planning, staff engagement, and effective quality management. Despite challenges in implementing accreditation, such as high costs, limited resources, and extensive documentation requirements, adequate resource support and strengthened leadership can help overcome these obstacles. Simplifying accreditation procedures is also necessary to ensure successful implementation across various types of hospitals. This study concludes that hospital accreditation is an effective tool for improving healthcare service quality, with implementation tailored to existing conditions and challenges

Keywords: Accreditation; Healthcare Service Quality; Hospitals; Patient Satisfaction; Quality Management

1. Introduction

Accreditation is one of the key instruments for improving the quality and safety of healthcare services. This process involves a comprehensive evaluation of the operational standards implemented in healthcare facilities, ensuring that institutions can meet patient needs with guaranteed quality [1]. Accreditation not only serves as an assessment tool but also as a continuous improvement mechanism to maintain and enhance service quality. Every accreditation system is designed to assess the extent to which a healthcare institution meets established standards. These standards cover various aspects such as patient safety, healthcare worker competence, service efficiency, and patient satisfaction. By implementing these standards, healthcare facilities can create a more conducive environment for delivering optimal services to the community [2].

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Despite its many benefits, accreditation implementation often faces various challenges, including limited human resources, high costs, and a lack of understanding of the accreditation process. These challenges can hinder the achievement of accreditation goals, which are to improve the overall quality of healthcare services [3]. Research has shown that accredited healthcare facilities tend to have higher patient satisfaction levels. This is because the accreditation process drives improvements in service quality, better communication, and a more patient-centered approach. Patient satisfaction becomes a crucial indicator in evaluating the success of accreditation.

Patient safety is a top priority in every accreditation program. With clear standards and proper implementation, accreditation can help reduce medical risks, such as medication errors or nosocomial infections. This directly enhances patient trust in healthcare facilities [4]. Accredited healthcare facilities generally demonstrate significant differences in service quality compared to those that are not accredited. This is due to the consistent implementation of standards and ongoing quality improvement efforts. However, external factors, such as government policies and budget allocation, can also influence service quality.

A literature review is necessary to comprehensively analyze various studies on the impact of accreditation on improving the quality of healthcare services. By identifying findings from multiple studies, researchers can develop relevant recommendations to support the effective implementation of accreditation. This research is essential to provide a clearer picture of the impact of accreditation on healthcare service quality [5]. The findings are expected to serve as a reference for policymakers, healthcare facility managers, and medical practitioners in designing better strategies to enhance service quality through the accreditation process

2. Methods

In conducting the literature review on "The Impact of Accreditation on Improving Healthcare Service Quality," methodological steps were undertaken to gain comprehensive insights. Establishing research objectives as an initial step clarified the scope and focus of the study. Subsequently, identifying critical keywords served as a guide for searching literature related to the impact of accreditation on improving healthcare service quality.

Figure 1 PRISMA Flow Diagram

The literature search process was conducted to collect relevant sources related to the research theme. The next step involved evaluating the quality of the selected literature by considering the research methodology, data validity, and relevance to the research focus. Extracted data were grouped based on the main themes, namely, factors hindering the

implementation of hospital management information systems. The following stages included analyzing and synthesizing the literature to identify patterns, trends, and findings related to the barriers to implementing management information systems in hospitals.

This process included extracting significant information, interpreting findings, and drafting conclusions. Conclusions and recommendations were derived through the preparation of a report that included the results of the literature evaluation, providing a holistic view of the barriers, and directing improvements in the implementation of hospital management information systems. This approach ensures that the research not only details the barriers but also contributes to a deeper understanding of solutions and implementable recommendations [5].

3. Results

To gather information on the impact of accreditation on improving healthcare service quality, the author conducted a search for articles using pre-designed keywords. The initial search yielded 28 articles, which then underwent a selection process to identify the most relevant articles. Following the selection, 15 articles from both international and national sources published between 2014 and 2024 were chosen. Through descriptive analysis, the primary focus was placed on the Impact of Accreditation on Improving Healthcare Service Quality. The findings from this literature review were then systematically compiled into a table to provide a comprehensive overview of the research theme.

Table 1 Research Articles on the Theme of the Impact of Accreditation on Improving Healthcare Service Quality

No	Year/ Author	Title	Findings
1	(Loai M. Zabin, Baraa F. Shayeb, Amani A. Abu Kishek, and Mohammed Hayek, 2024)	Nursing perception towards the impact of JCI accreditation on the quality of care in a university hospital in Palestine: a cross-sectional study	A study involving 180 nurses generally supported the positive impact of JCI accreditation on improving hospital quality processes. Over 90% of respondents acknowledged the role of accreditation in enhancing resource utilization, meeting population needs, and promoting professional standards and values among staff. Statistical analyses, including Pearson correlation and stepwise regression, showed a strong positive relationship between quality process variables and quality outcomes. Specifically, leadership commitment, strategic planning, and staff engagement were significant predictors of improved quality outcomes (Zabin et al., 2024).
2	(Coss-Mandiola et al., 2023)	Accreditation of Quality in Primary Health Care in Chile: Perception of the Teams from Accredited Family Healthcare Centers	A total of 26 categories were identified related to supporting and hindering factors in the process. From the axial phase, key categories were established, including quality management policies, the structure of Primary Health Care (PHC), participation and joint construction, as well as leadership and change management (Coss-Mandiola et al., 2023).
3	(Zhang et al., 2023)	The Impact of JCI Accreditation on the Clinical, Operational, and Financial Performance of Chinese Private Hospitals	Regression analysis showed that JCI accreditation was significantly associated with cesarean section rates, outpatient visits, delivery numbers, and revenue. However, JCI accreditation had no statistically significant association with three other clinical measures, including episiotomy rates, macrosomia incidents, and premature birth rates (Zhang et al., 2023).
4	(Swathi S, Dr. Srinath T K2, Suplab Kanti Podder3, 2023)	Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction with Reference to NABH Accredited Hospitals	The findings indicated a significant influence of effective service quality on customer satisfaction. High-quality services created an environmental ecosystem that facilitated hospitals and patients with an optimal care experience, post-treatment support, etc. (S et al., 2023).
5	(Ahlam Gamal Tolba, Fatma Gouda)	Effect of Joint Commission International Hospitals	The majority of study participants (97.6%) perceived a positive impact of JCI hospital accreditation, while the

	Metwally, and Zienab Ibrahim Ismail, 2021)	Accreditation on quality of Health care	majority (84%) rated the quality of health services as satisfactory. The mean total score and standard deviation related to healthcare quality were (90.05±21.71), representing 85.8% of the total score (Gamal Tolba et al., 2021).
6	(Solehudin & Sihura, 2023)	The Impact of Accreditation on Improving Hospital Service Quality	The study results indicated that accreditation influenced the quality of hospital services, with a trend of improving service quality scores from January to December 2022 (Solehudin & Sihura, 2023).
7	(Aldossary et al., 2022)	The Impact of Accreditation on Patient Safety and Quality of Care as Perceived by Nursing Staff in a Cardiac Care Centre in the Eastern Province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia	Hospital accreditation impacted patient safety, including nursing documentation, patient medication information, healthcare-associated infections, leadership, and support (Aldossary et al., 2022).
8	(Mohammad J. Alhawajreh, Audrey S. Paterson, William J. Jackson, 2023)	Impact of hospital accreditation on quality improvement in healthcare: A systematic review	Despite contradictory findings on the impact of accreditation on improving healthcare quality, accreditation continues to gain international acceptance as a quality assurance tool to support best practices in evaluating healthcare service quality outcomes. Policymakers, healthcare organizations, and researchers should proactively consider a range of key factors for future accreditation program implementation to ensure its effective execution and sustainability in hospital settings (Alhawajreh et al., 2023).
9	(Mojgan Zarifraftar, 2018)	Ranking of Challenges of Accreditation Standards Implementation in Public and Private Hospitals: A Comparative Approach	Exploratory factor analysis showed that challenges in implementing accreditation standards were grouped into nine main aspects, collectively explaining 72.4% of the variance. These factors included motivational drivers, perceptions of accreditation standards, financial resources, quality improvement, knowledge, skills, management commitment, regulatory support initiatives, standards development and surveys, human resources, and macro-level policy and procedure determination. The study also revealed ranking differences in these challenges between public and private hospitals, reflecting variations in needs and obstacles specific to each type of hospital (Zarifraftar, 2020).
10	(Inomata et al., 2018)	The Impact of Joint Commission International Accreditation on Time Periods in the Operating Room: A Retrospective Observational Study	Total procedure time did not change significantly, pre-anesthesia time increased, and induction time decreased following JCI accreditation (Inomata et al., 2018).
11	(Putri et al., 2022)	Differences in Health Service Quality Between Accredited and Non-Accredited Health Centers in North Kolaka Regency in 2021	The study identified key dimensions related to accreditation, including reliability, responsiveness, tangibles, empathy, and assurance (Putri et al., 2022).
12	(Phonna et al., 2021)	Nurses' Perceptions of the Impact of Accreditation on Healthcare Quality	Generally, accreditation had both positive and negative impacts. Positive impacts included improved facilities and infrastructure, regulations aligned with standards, enhanced staff knowledge and skills, better documentation systems, improved service quality, and protection of patient and staff safety, along with a better

			organizational culture. Negative impacts included increased documentation workload, higher work burdens, lack of staff involvement, high costs, and challenges in meeting facilities and infrastructure standards (Phonna et al., 2021).
13	(Babakkor & Kattan, 2023)	Accreditation Impact on Quality of Healthcare Organization Services and Culture in a Tertiary Hospital in Saudi Arabia	There was a significant positive relationship between employees' perceptions of accreditation and their professional environment (Babakkor & Kattan, 2023).
14	(Balci et al., 2021)	Accreditation Impact on Service Quality in Medical Laboratories: University Hospital Staff Viewpoints	The most critical factor was quality management, accounting for the largest proportion (52.0%) of the total variance. The second factor, accreditation benefits, explained 7.7% of the variance, consisting of seven scale items. The third factor, staff involvement in accreditation, contributed 6.7% of the variance and included three items. The fourth factor, quality outcomes, accounted for 4.6%. Lastly, the utilization of human resources explained 4.0% of the total variance with three items (Balci et al., 2021).
15	(Gökmen Kavak et al., 2020)	The Importance of Quality and Accreditation in Health Care Services During the Process of Combating COVID-19	The established standards included risk management, employee health and safety, patient safety, end-of-life care, infection prevention, medication management, sterilization management, laboratory services, waste management, outsourcing, material and device management, adverse event reporting, corporate communication, and social responsibility, all 100% related to COVID-19 processes (Gökmen Kavak et al., 2020).

Research on the impact of accreditation on improving the quality of healthcare services provides deep insights into how accreditation can enhance various aspects of hospital service quality. [6] revealed that more than 90% of nurses in university hospitals in Palestine expressed support for the positive impact of JCI accreditation. This accreditation has been shown to improve resource utilization, meet population needs, and promote the implementation of professional standards. Key factors influencing this success include leadership commitment, strategic planning, and staff engagement, all of which contribute to better quality service outcomes.

[7] found that in the accreditation process of accredited primary health care (PHC) centers in Chile, the main factors supporting success were quality management policies, PHC structures, strong leadership, and change management. Increased participation and joint construction among stakeholders were also deemed important in achieving effective accreditation. [8] revealed that in NABH-accredited hospitals, better service quality significantly influenced customer satisfaction levels. High-quality services created a supportive environment for patients, which in turn enhanced the patient care experience and strengthened the relationship between patients and the hospital.

[9] indicated that the majority of respondents felt that JCI accreditation had a positive impact on healthcare service quality. JCI-accredited hospitals achieved higher service quality levels, with an average quality score of 90.05, reflecting high satisfaction with the services provided. [10] found that JCI accreditation was significantly associated with several hospital performance indicators in China, including cesarean section rates, outpatient visits, and hospital revenue. Although accreditation was not significantly associated with all clinical metrics, its impact on hospital operational and financial performance remained positive, leading to more efficient resource utilization.

The results of these various studies demonstrate that hospital accreditation, whether by JCI or NABH, positively impacts healthcare service quality. Accreditation not only enhances service standards but also improves patient satisfaction, patient safety, and hospital operational performance. Factors such as leadership commitment, staff participation, quality management, and efficient resource utilization play a critical role in maximizing the benefits of accreditation. Furthermore, accreditation contributes to the sustainability of best practices in healthcare services, making it an essential tool for improving hospital quality and efficiency.

4. Discussion

Hospital accreditation is a critical tool in ensuring the quality and safety of healthcare services. The accreditation process is designed to standardize healthcare practices, providing assurance to patients that they receive safe and high-quality care [11]. Several studies have shown that accreditation positively impacts healthcare quality, including improved compliance with standard operating procedures (SOPs), better risk management, and increased efficiency in service delivery. However, these benefits often depend on organizational commitment and the availability of adequate resources.

Despite its clear advantages, the implementation of accreditation also faces significant challenges. Studies indicate that the process may encounter obstacles such as a lack of understanding of accreditation standards, limited financial resources, and resistance from healthcare workers. In public hospitals, these challenges are often more pronounced compared to private hospitals due to budget constraints and more complex bureaucracy. Therefore, a structured approach and support from various stakeholders are key to overcoming these barriers.

Additionally, one of the primary impacts of accreditation is the transformation of organizational culture towards continuous quality improvement. The accreditation process encourages healthcare workers to be more involved in decision-making and ensures that every step of service delivery focuses on patient needs [1]. However, in some cases, the administrative burden associated with accreditation can pose a challenge by reducing the time spent on direct patient interactions. This highlights the need to balance accreditation requirements with clinical service priorities.

Accreditation also contributes to increased transparency and accountability in healthcare services. The process promotes systematic data collection and performance evaluation, enabling hospitals to identify areas needing improvement. Furthermore, ongoing evaluations can assist hospitals in establishing evidence-based quality improvement strategies [12]. However, the effectiveness of this process relies on the involvement of all stakeholders, including management, healthcare workers, and patients. Accreditation holds significant potential to enhance healthcare quality, but its success heavily depends on contextual factors such as management support, healthcare staff training, and adequate resource allocation. With an integrated approach, hospitals can maximize the benefits of accreditation as a tool for improving service quality and meeting the expectations of patients and other stakeholders.

The literature review findings reveal the impact of accreditation on improving healthcare quality in various hospital settings. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive focus on human, organizational, technological, and managerial aspects. Strategic measures, such as infrastructure improvement, human resource training, and the development of uniform policies, must be implemented to ensure the successful adoption of hospital management information systems (SIMRS) and achieve optimal potential in healthcare information management.

Hospital accreditation, particularly those based on international standards such as the Joint Commission International (JCI), significantly impacts healthcare quality improvement. Studies show that accreditation enhances resource utilization, strategic planning, and staff engagement in supporting service quality. Strong leadership, change management, and regulatory support are critical factors in ensuring effective accreditation implementation [6]. Furthermore, accreditation increases the commitment to patient safety through better risk management, documentation, and medication management. However, significant challenges exist in implementing accreditation, particularly in public hospitals. Identified barriers include limited financial resources, inadequate staff knowledge and skills, and regulatory complexities. These challenges tend to vary between public and private hospitals, reflecting their respective needs and contextual obstacles [13]. Nevertheless, the benefits of accreditation, such as improved facilities and infrastructure, better operational standards, and the reinforcement of organizational culture, provide a strong justification for the continued development of accreditation programs.

Accreditation also positively impacts patient satisfaction, particularly by improving reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and tangible service evidence. However, studies show that the burden of documentation and high costs can be negative impacts, ultimately affecting hospitals' ability to fully meet accreditation standards. Therefore, a balance is needed between meeting standards and managing operational efficiency [14].

Hospital accreditation significantly contributes to improving the quality of healthcare services, although both positive and negative impacts must be managed wisely. Policymakers and hospital administrators must consider comprehensive strategic approaches to ensure the sustainability of accreditation programs [15]. With strong leadership support, staff participation, and adequate resources, accreditation can serve as an effective tool for enhancing the quality and safety of healthcare services

5. Conclusion

Hospital accreditation, especially with international standards such as the Joint Commission International (JCI), has been proven to have a significant positive impact on improving the quality of healthcare services. Accreditation drives better resource utilization, meets population needs, strengthens professional standards, and creates a safer and more effective service ecosystem. Additionally, accreditation supports leadership enhancement, strategic planning, and staff engagement, contributing to improved patient safety and organizational culture. However, the implementation of accreditation also faces challenges, such as high documentation burdens, resource limitations, and significant costs, which can be obstacles, particularly for hospitals with budget constraints.

Although some studies show inconsistent results regarding its impact on specific clinical indicators, accreditation is still internationally recognized as an essential quality assurance tool to support continuous improvement in healthcare services. Therefore, accreditation should continue to be promoted as part of efforts to enhance the quality and safety of services in healthcare facilities.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to the publication of this research.

Author Contributions

All authors made significant contributions to this research, including study design, data collection and analysis, and manuscript preparation. All authors have reviewed and approved the final version of this article

Statement of ethical approval

This research was conducted in accordance with applicable ethical guidelines. All research procedures have been aligned with relevant ethical standards to ensure the integrity and validity of the findings.

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